

Procedure.—A drop of the reagent was taken on a microscope slide and was touched with a small platinum loop dipped in a solution of caesium nitrate. After 3 or 4 minutes, beautiful octahedral crystals appear when viewed through a microscope (magnification 400 times). The limit of identification has been measured to be 4×10^{-8} g. (0.04 γ). The test is specific for caesium, rubidium and potassium do not interfere. It appears to be more sensitive than the triple caesium-silver-gold chloride test advocated by Emich. It is advisable to use the alkali (caesium) salt in the form of a nitrate.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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Condensation of Cotarnine and *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde.

BY K. N. KAUL AND G. S. AHLUWALIA.

Ahluwalia, Kaul and Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 197) have condensed cotarnine with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and formulated the product as *o*-nitrobenzoylhydrocotarnine following Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1458). A later note of Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 840), in which this formulation has been modified, escaped our attention. The analytical values for nitrogen come within experimental error whether $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3$ or $C_{19}H_{18}O_6N_2$ is accepted. A carbon hydrogen determination was considered unnecessary because it was not realised that there could be anything wrong with Robinson and Robinson's formulation.

Our attention has been drawn to this later note of Robinson and Robinson. Therefore we desire to correct our formulation of the condensation product and bring it in line with the later formula of these authors.

In fact we stated that "following Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1458) the compound was formulated as I" (*loc. cit.*).

UNIVERSITY CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF THE PUNJAB, LAHORE.

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